

Chapter 2. Visions of a sustainable world – for nature and people

Supplementary Materials

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Annex 2.1. Identification of sources and reliability assessment

To understand the transformative potential of visions, an approach was developed¹ to first identify sources of potential visions encompassing biodiversity, nature and nature's contributions to people and then divide the search into content areas as shown in **table SM.2.1**. An Intercoder reliability assessment² was conducted.

Table SM.2.1. Topics and materials of selected visions as well as methods used to analyze them.

Vision category	Topics / materials	Methods
SOURCES OF VISIONS		
Peer-reviewed literature	Visions, nature, transformations (and synonyms of each).	Keyword based searches; search terms; Web of Science review. To accommodate a wider diversity of visions, a more targeted search strategy was used, focusing on specific topics of high relevance for creating a more sustainable world.
Grey literature	Sector (non-governmental organizations, government, business, civil society, protected area plans, urban plans, land management plans, political, ocean, etc.); sector orientation of vision (global, holistic, business, economics, non-profit, political, civil society, health, education); discipline (humanities, science, economics, social sciences, technology).	General web-based search. Brainstorming supplemented by web-based searches, input from authors and others, references from websites and found documents and snowball sampling ³ to encompass a broad array of potential visions. Most grey literature was coded within appropriate content categories.
Initiatives and social movements	Organizations, narrative initiatives, urban, rural, landscapes, non-government organizations, business, Blue Economy, alternative economic visions, Indigenous and local knowledge, urban coalitions. Note that initiatives referring to these content	General web-based search. Brainstorming supplemented by web-based searches and snowballing partners and related initiatives on the websites of identified initiatives. As these visions were analyzed, most

¹ Systematic literature review using a keyword-based search focused on visions of transformative change related to biodiversity and nature, nature's contributions to people (NCP) and good quality of life (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10252319>)

² Intercoder reliability within the vision database (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14258309>)

³ Snowball sampling undertaken by looking at citations in the references of gathered sources and through inquiries with other assessment authors familiar with specific topics, in order to expand the extent of visions collected.

	areas/subtopics have been allocated for coding within the relevant area.	were moved to relevant content area categories.
Declarations, manifestos and international agreements	Declarations and manifestos related to biodiversity and nature and people, including international agreements.	General web-based search for “declaration” or “manifesto”, screened out by whether a vision is present or not. Plus, snowballing from other sources.
Indigenous and local knowledge	Agricultural species and genetic resources; medicinal species; technical innovations for use of biological resources and traditional farming and lifestyle practices; traditional cultures and customary laws related to conservation and sustainable use of biological resources; traditional local marker products; and traditional ecological customary law.	Including Indigenous and local knowledge dialogues (to consult the scenarios and models task force and the Indigenous and local knowledge task force), previous IPBES assessment reports.
Spiritual and religious visions	Types of materials: canonical scriptures of global religions, texts from different mystic traditions including poetry, other literary pieces and responses from current religious organizations to biodiversity loss and nature’s decline. Topics: self-knowledge, union, transformation, liberation, etc.	Selection of texts to ensure diversity across spiritual and religious traditions. To be selected, the texts had to contain a vision as per chapter definition and include at least one reference to a “natural” element. Analysis: 1) preliminary interpretation; 2) identification of common themes across texts; 3) inductive coding; 4) deductive coding (using common code sheet across categories).
Fiction ⁴	Science-fiction novels, comics, movies and short stories.	There is no global review or database of science-fiction AND nature/biodiversity/nature’s contribution to people. Vision selection was based on expert recommendations and specialized blogs found using web-based searches ("biodiversity" + “natur*"+[“book" OR “movie" OR “story” OR "comics"], mostly in English and in French.
Artistic expressions	Art, music, poetry, street art, murals, food, etc.	Web-based searches; expert recommendations.

⁴ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

		Expressions identified beyond those capturing human-nature interactions to focus on those transforming human-nature relationships to inspire sustainable social-ecological futures.
Social media	Flickr; Facebook; Twitter; Instagram; YouTube.	
Case Studies		From the case study database ⁵ , explicitly focused on visions.
SUBTOPICS/CONTENT AREAS		
Global visions	Visions with international or global scope with a focus on biodiversity and nature.	Web-based searches; expert recommendations.
Biomes	Ocean (marine, coastal); freshwater (lakes, rivers, streams); land (grassland, forest, tundra, agriculture, landscapes).	Web-based searches; expert recommendations.
Rural visions	Includes rural organizations, rural people, farmers, peasants, agribusiness and other rural communities.	General web-based search for “rural organizations” or “farmers”, plus snowballing from links withing organizations and from other sources. Vision identification relied upon expert recommendations on key rural communities and organizations worldwide.
Urban visions	Coalitions, Networks, Databases (e.g., Transition Towns, Common Dreams); peri-urban.	Web-based searches; snowballing.
Alternative economic visions	Heterodox approaches to economics that encompass biodiversity, ecosystems service and nature, along with human welfare.	Peer reviewed and grey literature from the GANE (Global Assessment for a New Economics) scoping review literature base was reviewed for presence of BES-associated visions. Initiatives were included when there were BES-related visions stated, after reviewing the allies and partners associated with WEAll (Wellbeing Economy Alliance) (about 250 at the time of assessment).
Technology	Visions from the private sector, international organizations, governments, NGOs, networks and communities on how technology address nature and people.	Survey-based outreach; web-based searches.
Rights of Nature	Visions of organizations and movements that specifically focus on promoting the rights of nature.	Web-based searches; snowballing.

⁵ Case studies database with transformative potential and pitfalls (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10260233>)

Note that “(general) web-based search” refers to where appropriate search strings were used to identify relevant visons. Snowballing refers to searching for additional relevant content based on e.g., citations in articles collected through web-based searches, additional less structured web searches, leads suggested by experts in the relevant source field, suggestions from reviewers, etc. Further information is available in data management reports.

2.1.1. Alternative economic visions

As the biodiversity and ecosystem crises have become more evident, it has also become clearer that transformative changes in how business and economics are practiced are crucial to halt these losses and shift trajectories. The idea that economic growth can continue indefinitely on a planet with finite resources, questions the continuation of business-as-usual⁶ for economies and businesses, with both academic and practice-based critiques. Others question the notion that human population with associated demands for provisioning services that invariably draw from nature can continue growing without significant negative ecological impacts. Further, biodiversity and ecosystem loss is increasingly associated with inequality that arises from current economic practices, which are key drivers of biodiversity loss and ecosystem issues (Slingenberg et al., 2009).

Unrealistic or problematic assumptions in today’s mainstream or conventional economics, sometimes labelled neoliberal economics, include its unrelenting extractive and exploitive growth orientation, its acceptance of inequality and its emphasis on market primacy with the associated idea that markets can resolve social and ecological problems with limited or no governmental or policy intervention. Further, conventional economic theory, contrary to biological, cultural and ecological evidence that points to the importance of care, collaboration and synergies, posits that humans (and by extension their institutions and businesses) are self-interested profit maximizers rather than caring beings who, at least some of the time, work collaboratively, cooperatively and in partnership with each other for the common good. These assumptions give rise to a belief of human exceptionalism that separates humans from nature, which fosters the problematic belief that humans social and technological innovations will be able to resolve problems and crises. That is despite increasing evidence of what is now being called “polycrisis” – intertwined, intractable set of crises that threaten civilization and even human survival.

These issues with mainstream economics have become more prominent in recent years and have given rise to a number of alternative economic and business sector-specific visions that provide clear alternatives to today’s conventional economics⁷, including nature-based solutions that attempt to protect, restore and sustainably use nature, biodiversity and ecosystems in ways that also benefit humanity (Faivre et al., 2017; *GoNaturePositive!*, n.d.; *Nature Positive Initiative*, 2024; Liu et al., 2021; Seddon et al., 2020, 2021). Three of these alternative economic visions (described below), are synthesized and consolidated from a wide range of literature because their visions were developed collectively by many authors rather than in a single publication, emphasize particular alternatives to mainstream economics: ‘Circular (and green and bioeconomy) economics’, ‘Steady-state, degrowth and circular degrowth economics’ and ‘Shared socioeconomics (wellbeing, doughnut, life-centred) within planetary boundaries’. A fourth, ‘the economics of biodiversity’ arises from the Dasgupta Review of (ecological) economics and biodiversity. It includes recent efforts by various business-related and foundation actors to incorporate ecological and biodiversity

⁶ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

⁷ Systematic literature review on Initiatives and Social Movements, Grey Literature, Alternative Economic Visions (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13881161>)

issues into the thinking and practice in different sectors, which is an approach to ecological economics. The fifth vision discussed here draws from a paper that outlines a ‘natural social contract’, which deeply implicates economics and business practice transformations, as well as human relationships with nature and each other. Further, since the release of the 2019 IPBES Assessment of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, a number of reports, including from major business associations, analyze business and economic implications specifically with respect to biodiversity and suggest pathways forward, which are incorporated as relevant into these descriptions.

Circular (and green) Economy: Circular economy, which has been strongly forwarded by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation and considerably discussed in academic research, like green growth, financing for nature, the bioeconomy and/or what has been labelled ‘nature-smart development’, is a system designed to be restorative and regenerative with respect to use of raw materials and manufactured goods. Restoration replaces the ‘end-of-life’ concept for products. Energy systems are shifted towards renewable technologies. The bioeconomy uses biological research and innovation to develop innovations that can create both public and economic benefits (The White House, 2012), across a range of products that can include foods, feed, fibre, fuels and ‘fun’ (things like flowers) (Birner, 2018). Over time, the term has shifted from describing the biological basis for economically productive activities to using biological knowledge for new products and industrial process innovations (Birner, 2018; Enriquez, 1998). Circular economy business models focus on manufactured goods (and services that use raw materials) to: 1) reuse, extend their service life through repair, remanufacture, restoration and upgrades and retrofits; 2) turn old goods into as-new resources by recycling materials (sometimes called upcycling). The general idea of circular economies is that material throughput can be reduced by changing modes and technologies of consumption and production aimed at reducing demand for raw materials by maximizing the productivity of already circulating materials and that generates economic value out of all residuals. Circular economy is sometimes framed as ‘end of waste’, maximizing resource productivity to minimize useless/invaluable waste streams, turning ‘waste into wealth’, as input for economic innovation, while moving from waste to resource management. Values in this vision shift from ownership to stewardship of resources, consumers become prosumers—both users and creators of goods and services and social wealth would be considered in ‘stock’ not flow, in capital, not sales and growth would mean a rise in ‘quality and quantity of all stocks—natural, cultural, human and manufactured’. The circular economy vision for biodiversity is meant to eliminate waste. It thereby proposes reducing biodiversity threats by eliminating (reducing) pollution, greenhouse gases, single-use materials (design issue); it redesigns materials, products, systems; circulates products and materials to leave room for biodiversity because fewer virgin resources are being used and negative impacts from extraction are reduced; it regenerates nature to enable biodiversity to thrive by employing nature actively to regenerate natural systems (regenerative approach) in multiple biomes: land, ocean, freshwater.

A related circular economy biodiversity vision rethinking ‘big food’ production from a circular economy perspective argues for using diverse ingredients to increase genetic crop and livestock diversity, lower impact, upcycled and regeneratively produced ingredients also orients specifically towards reducing biodiversity loss. Although oriented towards fundamentally shifting how economies function with respect to production, the circular economy, bioeconomy and green growth visions are critiqued as business- and foundation-led, for retaining an economic growth orientation and because it rests on a technological ‘fix’ that goods can be re-used for long periods of time that is yet not fully tested without significantly shifting the purpose of economies.

Steady-state, degrowth and circular degrowth economics: This vision is a synthesis of degrowth, steady-state and circular degrowth economics that builds on an emerging perspective that steady-state and degrowth economics have numerous similar and increasingly merging characteristics, with economic degrowth in the global North providing a path for approximating a globally equitable steady-state economy by opening up the possibility for more economic growth in the South. ‘Degrowth’ is a translation from the French *‘décroissance’* (reduction), challenging ‘green growth’ and ‘green economy, which (like circular economies) retain a belief in continual economic growth. Degrowth economies visions have socially sustainable and equitable reduction (and stabilization) in society’s throughput, where throughput denotes the materials and energy a society extracts, processes, transports and distributes, to consume and return back to the environment as waste. A steady-state economy would be one that undergoes neither growth nor recession, resulting in a constant rate of throughput aligned with human population (Czech & Daly, 2004). Core principles emphasize ecology, that is a belief that ecosystems have value in themselves, not just for services provided and emphasize paths to preserve ecosystems, integration of humans into nature, which includes ‘rights of nature’ to preserve what remains and regenerate ecosystems. In degrowth and its growing connection with steady-state economics, the meaning of life/wellbeing is based on the economics of happiness. Further, degrowth ‘posits a society based on sufficiency, autonomy and democracy, liberated from the drive to consume and produce and therefore able to downscale economies’ material throughput, beginning with all excess’. Degrowth is based on the daily labour of reduction, recycling and reuse. To counteract waste, which degrowth economics considers a dangerous product of economy geared toward growth, like steady-state (and circular) economies, it envisions a society that reuses materials to satisfy needs and problematizes wasteful consumption, extractivism⁸, ever-increasing production and planned obsolescence⁸. Daly, who introduced the idea, defined steady-state economics as having constant stocks of physical wealth (artifacts) in line with a constant population that nature can support, controlling throughput beginning with extraction (depletion) of low entropy resources and ending with high entropy waste (pollution). Services yielded are the ultimate benefit, while throughput is the ultimate cost, subject to laws of thermodynamics.

Four key features of steady-state economy, similar to degrowth, include: 1) sustainable scale, 2) fair distribution, 3) efficient allocation and 4) high quality of life. Sustainable scale means that the size of economy fits within the capacity of ecosystems to provide resources/absorb wastes, thereby enhancing ecosystem services for humans. Fair distribution means that people have equal opportunities to obtain wealth and income and limits to inequality prevent big gaps between rich and poor. Efficient allocation means that power of markets is harnessed appropriately to allocate resources among competing uses. High quality of life means economic growth focuses on what really matters to people, health, well-being, secure employment, leisure time, strong communities and economic stability.

Shared socioeconomics (wellbeing, doughnut, life-centred) within planetary boundaries: Expressed in somewhat different ways and despite some differences, a growing number of economic approaches (working to counter mainstream economics) that go by different labels are converging around a vision that can broadly be called ‘shared socioeconomics within planetary boundaries’. This consolidated vision includes wellbeing economics, doughnut economics, life-Centred economics, real wealth of nations (caring economics), business for nature and regenerative business, encompassing a broad swath of ecological economics perspectives. Central to this approach is the idea of a ‘safe operating space’ or a ‘safe and just

⁸ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

space' for humans living in harmony with the natural environment by keeping the impacts of their activities within planetary boundaries. It also entails living with values oriented towards 'sufficiency' in resource consumption so that both physical and social provisioning systems are balanced with nature's capacities. Goals of this approach including reducing inequality, enhancing social supports, meeting the sustainability goals associated with the UN's Sustainable Development Goals, while shifting the economic agenda away from (financial, monetary and material) growth towards sustainable and equitable human wellbeing within planetary boundaries. Core values that focus on life-centred economics supporting this approach include: stewardship of the whole system (at multiple levels), co-creation⁹ of collective value, cosmopolitan localist governance shifting decision democratically and locally, ecological regeneratively, reciprocity and circularity, emphasis on relationality and connectedness and equitable markets and trade, while the Wellbeing Economy Alliance (WEAll) has similarly identified values of dignity, nature, connection, fairness⁹, participation, holistic wellbeing, quality of life and flourishing for all people sustainably for the planet. Key characteristics of these wellbeing-oriented economies and economies include fundamental goals of delivering good human mental and physical health, greater equality and fairness, good social relationships, in a flourishing natural environment. Activities (pathways) to generate these outcomes including giving value to economic activities driven by collaboration and sharing, recycling and upcycling, blurring boundaries between producers and consumers, regenerating ecosystems, extending the global commons, supporting safe and healthy communities, more equitably and fairly distributing wealth, using renewables and developing purpose-driven business with social and environmental aims and creating metrics that reflect real value creation.

Speaking directly to the biodiversity issue, Otero and colleagues building on O'Neill and others work, pick up many of these themes, offering Shared socioeconomic pathways (zero) as a foundational vision, consistent with WEAll, the Wellbeing Economy Alliance, a global coalition of 'new economy' efforts aimed at fostering what can broadly be characterized as wellbeing economies. This framing is also consistent with Raworth's articulation of 'doughnut economics' described as: 'A new model of human wellbeing that depends on enabling every person to lead a life of dignity and opportunity, while safeguarding the integrity of Earth's life-supporting systems within planetary boundaries'. This framework uses the planetary boundaries as an outer set of constraints and offers an inner set of social foundations of what people need as a minimal social foundation, with the 'doughnut' in between considered a safe operating space for humanity.

Economics of biodiversity: The economics of biodiversity vision derives from several comprehensive economics and biodiversity reports which made the case for systematic appraisal of the economic contribution of biodiversity and ecosystem services to human wellbeing⁹ (TEEB, 2010). More recently, the Dasgupta Review (Dasgupta, 2021) emphasizes the idea of 'natural capital' (nature, biosphere, natural world, natural capital) – defined as the value of natural resources – incorporated into economic models, along with human capital (value of human knowledge) to deal with species loss/biodiversity issue. It calls for a major economic shift to incorporate the economics of biodiversity and ecosystem services into economics. This vision articulates the following values: humans embedded in nature. The economics of biodiversity is the economics of the entire biosphere. Human ingenuity focused on the common good can raise global output indefinitely without transgressing biosphere boundaries, yet the biosphere is bounded, therefore so is the global economy. Nature nourishes and nurtures humans in more than economic ways therefore has intrinsic worth.

⁹ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

Nature is largely mobile and what are known as externalities are the ‘wedge’ between prices paid for natural goods and services and social values. Because many natural processes are silent (economically invisible), it is not always possible to trace harms on nature (and humans) to responsible parties. Self-monitor involves affection for natural processes and therefore a common future entails (all) humans to be naturalists.

The report recognizes that biodiversity means the diversity of life in all its forms, which is characteristic of ecosystems and enables systemic resilience. The biosphere is a regenerative entity, ecosystems are self-regulating (within bounds). They blend into each other—and all humans are part of ecosystems and dependent on them for provisioning and cultural services. Modern agriculture (monocultures) produces a lot of food at the cost of biodiversity. Four approaches (pathways) for attaining ‘impact equality’ and enhancing biodiversity and ecosystem services are outlined: 1) reduce per capita global consumption, 2) lower future global population from what it is today, 3) increase the efficiency with which the biosphere’s supply of goods and services are converted into global output and return to the biosphere as waste and 4) invest in nature through conservation and restoration to increase the stock of Nature and its regenerative rate (Dasgupta, 2021). An additional pathway to note may be where agricultural practices enhance biodiversity. Technological advances are often seen as engines of economic growth and there are assumptions that humanity will (eventually) be able to break free of nature. The report, however, makes clear that human economies are embedded in nature, therefore bounded. Three key transitions, along with numerous other changes, are identified: 1) ensure that (human) demands do not exceed nature’s supply, 2) change measures of economic success towards sustainable paths and 3) transform institutions and systems to enable changes for future generations.

Natural social contract: The final vision is a holistic one that includes economics and goes well beyond it to envision that the nature of the societal, environmental and economic problems facing humanity today could be improved by a new social contract, coined as a natural social contract. This approach envisions a society that is more humane and fairer and above all less destructive to people and nature. ‘A natural social contract does justice to a human being’s natural state (human life is group life) and to the natural position of humankind and society within a larger ecosystem, that of planet Earth. It regards society as a social-ecological system, focusing on people as members of a community and as part of a natural ecosystem’. As the authors put it, ‘a natural social contract emphasizes long-term sustainability and general welfare by combining human and nature and recalibrating while at the same time putting an end to unlimited economic growth, overconsumption and over-individualization, for the benefit of ourselves, the planet and future generations’. Core and in line with the United Nations’ Sustainable Development Goals is making society more fair, equal, sustainable, in a holistic approach based on values of responsibility developed within hybrid sphere and alternative economy. This vision incorporates doughnut, wellbeing and economy for the common good concepts economically, recognizes the need for co-evolutionary processes and inherent interconnectedness¹⁰ among beings on Earth. It adopts values around institutional design that emphasize adaptive, reflexive deliberative governance, equal and fair (re-)distribution of risks, costs and benefits, arrangements for collective decision-making, reflexive monitoring of impacts and outcomes, conflict prevention and resolution mechanisms and policy learning.

¹⁰ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

2.1.2. Declarations, manifestos and global agreements

Multiple important declarations, manifestos and global agreements were investigated, including a recent declaration titled The Africa Want Vision 2063, for their linkages to biodiversity and ecosystem services. Notably, most such declarations emphasize human rights¹⁰ and wellbeing with little or no reference to nature or biodiversity. Two documents that offer clearly defined biodiversity and ecosystem services visions stand out: the United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD, 1992) and the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (United Nations, 2015). Given the large-scale loss of biodiversity across the globe (particularly over the last two to three decades), the intention to promote environmental sustainability is often first stated or declared at an international level. Legally binding mechanisms to protect biodiversity at both national and international levels are promoted, where there is involvement and buy-in of a broad range of stakeholders. For example, the Convention on Biological Diversity is an “international legally-binding treaty with three main goals: conservation of biodiversity; sustainable use of biodiversity; and the fair and equitable sharing of the benefits arising from the utilization of genetic resources.”

In both visions, there is an emphasis to include women and Indigenous Peoples and local communities when focusing on the conservation of nature. There is also an emphasis to see biodiversity loss as a cross-cutting issue across economies, society and the environment, which cannot work in isolation when the goal is to harmonize people and nature. For example, the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, provides a “shared blueprint for peace and prosperity for people and the planet, now and into the future,” which is underpinned by the 17 Sustainable Development Goals. The Sustainable Development Goals acknowledge that ending poverty and other deprivations go together with strategies that improve health and education, reduce inequality and spur economic growth – all while tackling climate change and working to preserve oceans and forests (United Nations, 2015). One of the core underlying visions in the 2030 Agenda is a world where humanity lives in harmony with nature and biodiversity is protected.

Following the release of the 2019 IPBES Global Assessment of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES, 2019a), a number of important reports have been issued to highlight the types of measures and visions that are needed to reduce biodiversity loss. One important framework is the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (CBD, 2022), which is an agreed plan that articulates pathways towards harmonizing people and nature by ensuring responsibility and transparency, reducing threats and meeting people's needs. Specific goals consider ecosystems, species and genetic diversity; ensuring that human needs are met sustainably, that benefits are shared equitably and appropriate means of implementation developed. The Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework 2030 action targets, to enable achievement of the 2050 Vision, include effectively conserving at least 30% of terrestrial, inland water and of coastal and marine areas, especially those of particular importance for biodiversity; reducing the rates of introduction and establishment of invasive alien species by at least 50%; reducing pollution risks and negative impacts of pollution by reducing loss of excess nutrients to the environment by 50% or more, reducing overall risk from pesticides by at least half and working towards eliminating plastic waste; using ecosystem-based approaches to minimize the impact of climate change and ocean acidification on biodiversity and substantially reducing harmful biodiversity incentives.

2.1.3. Global visions

Starting with early global visions for a sustainable world, such as the 1972 Club of Rome’s “Limits to Growth” report (Meadows et al., 1972), Schumacher’s “Small Is Beautiful”

(1973), the Ecologist “blueprints for survival”, Ehrlich’s “population bomb,” global visions have evolved from emphasizing concerns about ecological sustainability to visions encompassing sustainable growth and equity as a part of the envisioned future (Purvis et al., 2019). There is a divide in global visioning between those perpetuating sustainable growth through decoupling from material resource consumption and other environmental pressures and those envisioning quality of life and ecological sustainability as a premise for a sustainable future (Fioramonti et al., 2022). The initial critical standpoint towards economic growth found in the Declaration of the UN Conference on the Human Environment in Stockholm (1972) gave way to the consideration of economic growth as beneficial for the environment, specially from the Brundtland report (1987) onwards (Gómez-Baggethun & Naredo, 2015). The IPBES Global Assessment (IPBES, 2019a) marks a shift in this trend as it recognizes the need to move away from the growth paradigm¹¹ to conserve biodiversity.

Tallis et al. (2018) present what they perceive as an attainable vision for halting the loss of biological diversity while meeting demands from a growing population by changing the way food and energy is produced and distributed. While technically plausible, they also admit the political, economic and social challenges that need to be overcome to achieve this vision. Others emphasize the need of changing mindsets to protect nature and meet human needs, such as the vision of an ecological civilization and ‘unity of man and nature’ (Ma et al., 2020).

2.1.4. Urban visions

Roughly half of humanity lives in cities, with nearly 70 percent projected to do so by 2050 (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2018). The health and well-being of millions of people thus depends on how cities are presently designed and how urban areas are envisioned in the future (McPhearson et al., 2021; Munro & Grierson, 2018). Simultaneously, a rapid decline in nature and the most dramatic reduction in biodiversity is expected (IPBES, 2019a), due in part to the rapid growth in urban populations and their use of resources (Elmqvist et al., 2013). As a result, urban leaders have both an opportunity and responsibility to design cities for the well-being of urban dwellers and the natural systems on which they depend, designing in a manner that recognizes the diverse values of people and the vital benefits they accrue from nature (IPBES, 2022). Integrating urban design and nature conservation generates a compelling vision for sustainable and just¹¹ cities. Initiatives to include urban nature in future planning, to foster biodiversity within cities and to share knowledge and experience across cities are beginning to take hold (Guerry et al., 2021). Instead of attempting to assess individual city’s urban design plans and visions for integrating nature into the built environment, shared visions were sought that contained in urban coalitions or networks that share best practices across cities.

Using a web-based search and snowball techniques, urban coalitions, city-to-city networks or transnational city networks were identified. Although still being sourced and the database coded according to the vision assessment criteria, example visions are presented from the Biophilic Cities Network, which links cities, researchers and a diversity of actors interested in how nature in cities contributes to the lives of urban residents. Including several alternative visions, conceptualized around the work of E.O. Wilson and planning with nature at the centre where “the vision of life in a biophilic city is one where humans are immersed in nature; humans are not separate from, but intimately embedded in, nature”. In ‘The Half-earth city’, the central tenet comprises cities as laboratories for experimentation and

¹¹ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

innovation to find a balance between an improved quality of life and continued flourishing of human and nonhuman species alike. In addition to presenting alternative urban visions, the Biophilic Cities Network also showcases example cities living out the concept, such as Ciudad Dulce (“Sweet City”) in Curridabat, Costa Rica. Here the vision centres around enhancing the lived experience of its inhabitants through a collective consideration of biodiversity, infrastructure, habitat, coexistence and productivity.

An exemplary initiative is the Green City Initiative by the International Association of Horticultural Producers, which aims to transform urban areas into greener, healthier and more sustainable spaces. The initiative revolves around a set of comprehensive guidelines that advocate for integrating nature into urban environments, ensuring that green spaces are accessible and beneficial to all urban residents. Through these principles, the Green City Initiative promotes a holistic approach to urban development, where ecological, social and economic factors are balanced to enhance the quality of life in cities. The guidelines emphasize creating resilient urban ecosystems, fostering biodiversity and promoting environmental stewardship. This approach extends beyond the mere inclusion of green spaces, encouraging cities to adopt practices that support sustainable development¹², mitigate climate change and improve public health. By focusing on the integration of nature into urban planning, the Green City Initiative envisions cities where nature and people coexist harmoniously, ultimately contributing to more livable and equitable urban environments worldwide.

Another example comes from the Nature of Cities, an international platform that connects people interested in the design and creation of better cities for all, with the mission of curating conversations about urbanism across ways of knowing and modes of action. One of the diverse manners of doing so is through a published series of “26 Visions for Urban Equity, Inclusion and Opportunity”. Although variably focused on nature, the visions represent 22 cities across five continents and from myriad perspectives. Lastly, an example from Regeneration, which is more focused on peri-urban landscapes and roughly along a gradient from the urban core to rural landscapes. Here, “life [is] at the centre of every action and decision. It applies to all of life—grasslands, farms, insects, forests, fish, wetlands, coastlands and oceans—and it applies equally to family, communities, cities, schools, religion, commerce and governments. And most spectacularly to climate”. Although Regeneration does not present a vision *per se*, they explore regenerative solutions, looking for connections and providing frameworks for action centered on equity, reducing, protecting, sequestering, influencing and supporting.

2.1.5. Peer-reviewed literature

The peer-reviewed literature captures a specific set of visions for a desired future for nature and people. Desired futures are conceptualized by different academic traditions using different terminologies for visioning. Developing search criteria that capture visions that are broadly related to nature or people-nature relationships provides either a too narrow set of desired futures for nature and people by using (e.g., strict rules for inclusion, or a too broad set of targeting all drivers that potentially matters for sustainable futures). By applying exclusion criteria, relatively few visions targeting a desirable future for nature and people were found. It was therefore decided to use a more targeted search strategy by focusing on specific topics of high relevance for creating a flourishing world.

¹² See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

2.1.6. Grey literature¹³

In 2017, the basis for what is now the Nature Futures Framework (Lundquist et al., 2017, 2021; Pereira et al., 2020) introduced seven visions for nature's contribution to people: respectively titled "Nature-based Inclusive Prosperity", "Sustainable Food Systems", "ReFooding and ReWilding the Urban Rural Flows"; "Healthy Socio-Ecological Freshwater Systems"; "A Tasty World with Values", "Dancing with Nature"; and "Health Oceans, Happy Communities" (Lundquist et al., 2017). While focusing on different aspects of the nature people relationship, these visions mostly shared an emphasis on enhancing the role of nature to contribute to human wellbeing, recognition of the multi-functionality of nature, shifting away from Gross Domestic Product towards sustainable development, reduced inequity and healthy diets. Most emphasized combining high tech applications with optimal use of natural resources and strong cross-scale governance systems and generally moving towards scenarios that recognize the need for regional sustainable development.

Many reports issued since the 2019 IPBES Global Assessment respond to the impending biodiversity loss by advocating radically changing and transforming the way business is done. These reports are important because they outline specific details and pathways for businesses to change their operating systems to transform how they approach nature, including species loss. At the same time, they are oriented towards getting business 'buy in' to shift the business paradigm and mindsets in significant ways (Meadows, 1999). For example, the report from the World Bank Group in "Unlocking Nature-Smart Development: An Approach Paper on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services" is an explicitly biodiversity-oriented vision (World Bank Group, 2021). The report identifies biodiversity and ecosystem services as development issues – the decline of which will have negative economic impact, particularly on poorer countries. It claims to take a new approach for the World Bank that engages economic and financial decision makers to integrate nature-based solutions and/or ecosystem-based approaches into their investment strategies, enhance local benefits of conservation and sustainability, mobilizing finance for nature and developing new metrics and partnerships. This vision makes an economic case for nature to counter the biodiversity crises and deal with ecosystem risks. To accomplish these visions, the report outlines core building blocks that include a whole-of-economy approach to addressing drivers of biodiversity and ecosystem services losses, based on solid scientific evidence and measures to support an equitable and inclusive transition. The report targets six key response arenas: economic and financial decision makers, integration of nature-based solutions and/or ecosystem-based approaches into sector investments; enhancing local conservation and sustainability benefits; mobilizing finance; producing new metrics and tools that support integration of sustainability issues; and leveraging partnerships.

2.1.7. Indigenous and local knowledge

The IPBES Global Assessment (IPBES, 2019a) is the first comprehensive ecological assessment to systematically incorporate Indigenous and local knowledge at the global scale. As part of its mandate, IPBES has in its assessment processes worked with Indigenous and local knowledge, defined as "knowledge and know-how accumulated across generations, which guide human societies in their innumerable interactions with their surrounding environment" (Thaman et al., 2013). Weaving together Indigenous and local knowledge and other forms of knowledge, Indigenous Peoples and local communities have shaped the

¹³ Systematic literature review on Initiatives and Social Movements, Grey Literature, Alternative Economic Visions (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13881161>)

ecologies, conservation initiatives and resource economies of vast regions of the world (McElwee et al., 2020). Indigenous and local knowledge themes were identified that linked to agricultural species and genetic resources, medicinal species, technical innovations for use of biological resources and traditional farming and lifestyle practices, traditional cultures and customary laws related to conservation and sustainable use of biological resources, traditional local market products and traditional ecological customary law to explore Indigenous and local conceptualizations of the future and the inter-relationships with broader worldviews within these knowledge systems (Xue, 2011; Yin Lun, 2022).

We acknowledge that the premise of visions of transformative change itself represents a mismatch with Indigenous and local worldviews and conceptions of change. Visions of the future may be inconsistent with some Indigenous and local conceptions of time, which are not always linear. The concept of transformative change, similarly, may represent a risk to Indigenous and local communities. Transformative changes have been imposed on Indigenous Peoples, sometimes to devastating and long-term cultural, social and environmental effects. Indigenous and local knowledge continues to be marginalized in many decision-making processes. Acknowledging and addressing this reality will support a more equitable approach to transformative change. Finally, the knowledge of Indigenous Peoples and local communities can support new ways of thinking and understanding in other knowledge communities; drawing from Indigenous and local knowledge can support transformations towards an equitable and sustainable world globally (Vijayan et al., 2022).

Understanding that there is a wide diversity of Indigenous Peoples and local cultures and communities, a regional approach was taken to compile this information¹⁴, where regional experts were engaged to compile the following:

- Reflections on the resonance of the concept of “visions of transformative change for biodiversity” from Indigenous Peoples and local communities and potential opportunities and risks emerging from this framing of visions.
- Identification of sources of knowledge that are relevant to desired holistic aspirations for the future for systems that involve biodiversity or nature.
- Identification of practices, values and worldviews underlying those aspirations
- Explanation of case studies which exemplify these issues.

2.1.8. Spiritual and religious visions

Spirituality was considered as the search for the sacred in oneself and religion as the institutionalization of such search, which can be compatible or incompatible with spirituality depending on the context (de Kalbermatten, 2003; Hill et al., 2000). Thus, foundational texts of global religions (scriptures) were considered as potential containers of spiritual visions alongside other sources like non-canonical scriptures or literary pieces describing spiritual experiences beyond institutionalized religion (especially mystic poetry belonging to different linguistic traditions, see example in **box SM.2.1** below). These sources were written between the 8th century BCE and the early 20th century CE. Hence, they were not produced in response to the current biodiversity loss and nature’s decline. However, they hold important messages and provide inspirational resources for transformative change. Indeed, a common message emerged across these sources: the vision or promise of a potential human-nature connectedness which is explicitly or implicitly explained as a union with the divine. This

¹⁴ Visions from Indigenous and local knowledge (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13926219>)

connectedness or union is symbolically described using different elements of nature such as a garden, a fountain, a mountain, etc.

For example, the *Quran* (Yusuf Ali (trans.), n.d.) says “God hath promised to believers, men and women, gardens under which rivers flow, to dwell therein and beautiful mansions in gardens of everlasting bliss” (Sūra 9, v. 72). In resurrection times, “he will be in a life of bliss, in a garden on high, the fruits whereof (will hang in bunches) low and near. ‘Eat ye and drink ye, with full satisfaction’” (Sūra 69, v. 21-24). The Javanese poem *Dharma Śūnya*, attributed to Kamalanatha, says “There is a river, ancient and remote, which penetrating through the mountain’s centre, emerges at its summit; On that summit there is a pearl, glittering like crystal, its pureness constantly radiating forth, within it is the nectar of immortality – he who finds it is able to achieve the highest bliss of firm union, the recognition of concepts ceases and one experiences supreme pleasure, beyond the power of words to describe” (Canto III, v. 3)(Noyce, 2002). A key message emerging from the visions collected is that self-knowledge or self-realization (the process through which spiritual practitioners become aware and experience this connectedness or union) is related to blissful states of complete satisfaction and harmony. This provides inspiration, imagination and motivation for transformative change for people and nature. For example, (Ma et al., 2020) developed a Tao-inspired scientific response to the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework emphasizing the unity between humans and nature. Some visions contain references to radical transformations linked to self-knowledge. The transformation towards a new era is often enabled by the feminine aspect of the divine or the figure of a primordial Mother.

In addition to these classic sources, visions included in texts or declarations from current religious leaders, spiritual organizations and inter-faith initiatives which explicitly respond to the current biodiversity loss and nature’s decline were also selected. These visions are obviously more specific than the classic ones and use contemporary language to refer for example to direct and indirect drivers of biodiversity loss and nature’s decline¹⁵. This is the case for example of Pope Francis’ *Laudato Si'* (Francis, 2015) or the Multi-Faith Response to the Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework (Faiths for Biodiversity, n.d.). In these and other contemporary visions, religious beliefs are often mobilized to justify the need for humans to become stewards of ‘Creation’, which is considered to have intrinsic value. For example, “Towards a Global Ethic” commits to transform the moral foundations of unjust and greedy economic structures based on a common set of values across the world’s religions (Parliament of the World’s Religions, 2020). This challenges the dominant understanding of religions as enablers of human domination over nature and may signal a shift towards a perspective where humans are seen as part of rather than separate from nature.

Connecting the old spiritual wisdom from classic sources and the transformative efforts of current spiritual and religious initiatives there is the vision “Self-realization saves humans and nature” by Shri Mataji. This vision posits that humans can stop the degradation of nature if they get their self-realization through the awakening of a living energy called Kundalini, which enables blissful states of union, improved brain functioning, character traits such as forgiveness and hope and better sustainability-related decisions (Otero et al., 2024).

¹⁵ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

Box SM.2.1. Example of spiritual and religious vision: Forests of Kalpataru Trees.

May the all-pervading Lord now be pleased
with this literary sacrifice of mine.

And being pleased may He grant me the following boon:

May the wicked give up their wickedness
And develop a liking for good deeds
May all beings feel friendly with one another.

May the darkness of evil vanish
May the whole universe see the light, the sun of One Universal Religion.
May the desire of all human beings be fulfilled.

May the world be visited ceaselessly by the company of the faithful saints
Who would shower blessings on the earth.

Such men are the moving forests of Kalpataru trees
They are mines of wish-granting living jewels
They are vocal oceans of nectar.

They are moons without spots
suns without heat.
Let such saints be friends to all.

Written by Gyaneshwara in *Pasayadan* (1290 CE). Translation taken from Noyce (2002: 35)

In total, 33 visions were selected and coded under spiritual and religious visions, including both classic and contemporary sources¹⁶. These visions come from a wide array of spiritual and religious traditions of humanity: Judeo-Christian, Christian, Taoist, Buddhist, Hindu, Islamic, Mystic (Italian/Catholic, Spanish/Catholic, Persian/Sufi, Marathi/Hindu, English), Catholic, Sikh, Zoroastrian, Bahá'í, Sahaja Yoga, multi-faith, alchemy and other types of literature. Texts were read in their English translations.

¹⁶ Spiritual and religious visions (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13919783>)

2.1.9. Fiction

Positive eco-fictions contained in books and comics depict holistic visions of the future, with a systemic interweaving of the many dimensions of biodiversity and nature's contribution to people. Their narrative often emphasizes a direct driver of biodiversity's decline (e.g., climate change as in climate-fiction, pollution, resource overexploitation) and illustrates how characters are faced with decisions mixing technology constraints and personal values. In these tales, authoritarian governance often goes along with predatory multinational firms, challenging equity, power dynamics and solidarity interactions between individuals forced to compete. Despite dystopian appearances, characters make use of their knowledge and social networks to push forward transformative change, where positive visions finally emerge from collective actions. Optimism surfaces from the realistic and creative solutions found by the characters.

For example, the novel 'The Ministry for the Future' (Robinson, 2020) sets the stage in 2025 to depict the implementation and activities of an international taskforce "charged with defending all living creatures present and future who cannot speak for themselves." This realistic and positive vision combines short-term political pressures with hope for a fairer and more sustainable way of life.

2.1.10. Artistic expressions

Given the magnitude and diversity in type and source of artistic expressions, the subset of visions encompassing artistic expressions was merely illustrative of the types of art-based visions that abound. Artistic collections examined included dance initiatives, following as closely as possible the screening criteria developed for peer-reviewed literature, with an additional consideration as to who the visions were aiming to influence to the greatest extent. The analysis underlined the need for grouping of artistic visions into broader-level initiatives to capture the fuller reach of dance pieces/art collections, rather than confining selection to specific dances or art pieces. Most often, transformative-inspiring artistic expressions are posted in exhibitions on web platforms speaking to various human-nature interactions, locations, species or biomes, yet all providing hope for living in harmony with nature in a myriad of different ways. Diversity in artistic expressions reflects diversity in ways in which society can respond to loss of biodiversity and transform. Considered at the level of an individual art piece, perhaps the most striking is "Steps for Change" (IRD, 2019), the dance piece especially commissioned to accompany the IPBES Global Assessment (IPBES, 2019b) and which served as a pre-cursor to the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework by highlighting biodiversity loss and the urgent need for "a step change", or "transformative change" in current parlance.

2.1.11. Social media

Social media data¹⁷ from Flickr, Twitter, Instagram, Panoramio, Weibo, Facebook and YouTube were widely utilized in studies addressing 12 (out of 17) Sustainable Development Goals (Ghermandi et al., 2023). Social media data commonly include images, videos and text (with associated metadata, such as time and often also place), made publicly available online by social media users. Social media, while it may not fully represent the most vulnerable communities, provides valuable insights into human behaviour, values, narratives and other dimensions related to the environment. As internet penetration continues to expand, the data

¹⁷ Social media analysis (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13844092>)

collected from these platforms offer unprecedented evidence of how people interact with and perceive environmental issues (Toivonen et al., 2019). Flickr and Twitter have gained more attention in the literature due to more open data access policies; among these two, Twitter as a textual data provider is the most relevant to the visions related to the environment. However, as Twitter narratives are usually laconic, visions of the desirable future are often indistinguishable from strategic goals – e.g., vision of circular economy principles: reduction of environmental impacts of industrial production driven by better waste and water management, extended producer responsibility schemes and renewable energy sources (De Lima, 2022). Social media-driven attempts to envision the future of biodiversity and conservation include a YouTube-based vision of orangutan conservation in Indonesia and Malaysia - "a future in which rescue and rehabilitation is no longer a necessary part of orangutan conservation" (Freund et al., 2021). Instagram-based visions are often expressed by 'green' influencers promoting sustainable consumerism¹⁸, e.g., "a cleaner world... of a connectedness with nature" (Lehbrink, 2020). The dissemination and power of visions in supporting transformative change may be enhanced through their portrayal in popular media and may become especially powerful when embodied in blockbuster movies and other international media phenomena that may be broadly promoted by celebrities. For example, visions of positive Ocean Futures have been successfully spread worldwide through partnership with UNEP Advocate for Life below Water Jason Momoa (Aquaman). Strategies for connecting visions with internationally popular media and celebrities, including partnerships with UN and UNEP 'ambassadors', have strong potential for improving their transformative potential.

At the same time, a systematic account of non-expert visions of the future on social media still needs to be explored - especially as explicit mention of 'vision' in the context of the future is heavily biased towards the expert, business and political communities, e.g., researchers explored Twitter communities around @GretaThunberg and major establishments such as @UNESCO and United Nations Secretary-General @AntonioGutierrez, @EU_Commission, united by a joint general vision of a more sustainable future (Ballestar et al., 2020). Future is among the top 10 most frequent words in English Twitter sustainability discourse (Tóth, 2022), but extracting meaningful vision from this discourse might be challenging. Non-English envisioning narratives comprise another research gap.

Therefore, environmental visions shared via social media X (formerly Twitter) were also searched. 271,109 tweets were collected via Twitter Academic API with search terms "vision biodiversity", "vision environment", "vision nature", "vision ecosystem", "future environment", "future biodiversity", "future nature" for 1-year period between 05.25.2022 and 05.25.2023. A topic modelling procedure was conducted as implemented in the BERTopic algorithm (Grootendorst, 2022), classifying tweets into 444 topics. Then, the topics were manually screened through, excluding non-relevant ones and tweets with an accuracy classification score of <0.5. For the remaining 7,925 tweets, their relevance was additionally screened and 962 tweets containing some kinds of positive visions for the future of nature and people were retained. Twenty of the most frequent topics in tweets are presented in **figure SM.2.1**.

¹⁸ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

Figure SM.2.1. Common tweets’ topics – ocean-related topics dominate, followed by water- and cycling-related tweets. A zero-shot topic modelling algorithm was used with a large multilingual model, facebook/bart-large-mnli (Yin et al., 2019) and the following candidate labels, reflecting the Nature Futures Framework: 'nature', 'culture' and 'society'. As marketing purposes were detected in some of the manually checked tweets, another candidate label was also used, 'greenwashing'. Greenwashing was understood in a sense as defined by The European Supervisory Authorities' high-level common definition: "a practice where sustainability-related statements, declarations, actions, or communications do not clearly and fairly reflect the underlying sustainability profile of an entity... sustainability-related misleading claims can occur and spread either intentionally or unintentionally" (ESMA, 2023).

As a result, **figure SM.2.2** demonstrates the relevance of the most common visions of desirable future shared via X (Twitter) to instrumental (society), relational (culture), intrinsic (nature) values with an indicator of their greenwashing potential. The automated greenwashing potential estimation is intended only to demonstrate the presence of narratives, which would need further investigation on a case-by-case basis and be treated with caution. Nevertheless, it was observed that mining, shipping, tourism and fashion industries are likely to operationalize sustainability discourse for marketing purposes. This strategy might indicate greenwashing potential and constitutes the respective research gap. In turn, topics related to ecosystems – mangrove forests, mushrooms, wetlands, as well as to biodiversity and trees plantations are less likely to contain some kind of greenwashing. Topics of higher greenwashing potential are located closer to 'culture' and 'society', reflecting instrumental (e.g., mining) and relational (tourism, plastic pollution) values of nature.

Figure SM.2.2. Common topics of the tweets, sorted in order of decrease in greenwashing potential. Dot size indicates likelihood of greenwashing.

Social media data contain a largely unexplored volume of the visions of a better future for people and nature. However, making big data 'small and meaningful' (Poorthuis & Zook, 2017) to derive them creates new challenges since explicit mentions of such futures and visions are more common for business actors, policymakers and activists, while broad public opinions remain in the shadows. Still, natural language processing, computer vision and artificial intelligence tools gradually address this gap and provide new opportunities for extracting relevant information from big data.

2.1.12. Case studies

A case study example was specifically selected from Villasante et al. (2021) that offers an inspirational vision: After the abrupt shock and the huge impacts of the Prestige oil spill in 2002, artisanal fishers from Lira (north-central coast of Galicia, Spain) initiated a process or preparation phase to create a 'Marine Reserve of Fishing Interest' (hereinafter referred to as marine protected area) that concluded with its formalisation in April 2007, with the name of *Os Miñarzos*. Under the Fisheries Law of the *Xunta de Galicia* (Law 11/2008, December 3, of Galician Fishing), marine reserves of fishing interest are tools for the management of fishing resources and conservation of marine ecosystems. In the process of creating the marine protected area of *Os Miñarzos*, fishers have taken an active participation in the design and collectively defined the most suitable management plans (mainly through a co-management system) for sustainable fishing within the reserve, which led to a greater acceptability and compliance of norms, entering the navigation phase (Villasante et al., 2021).

More than 17 years after its full implementation, the transformative change that took place since the creation of the marine protected area not only had repercussions on fishing practices and outcomes (e.g., higher abundance of species and economic revenues), but also on the beliefs and social values of the main fishers, scientists and representatives of the regional administration involved in the Management Body of the marine protected area. Trust and cooperation, essential elements to successfully govern common pool resources, have been improved since fishers provide data and participate in different monitoring programmes. There has also been a notable reduction of conflicts and mistrust between the administration and the fisheries sector, favouring that most decisions concerning fishing activities within the marine protected area are taken by consensus. Another sign of progress was the collective

behaviour of local fishers working within the marine protected area who, after the decision of the regional administration to discontinue financially supporting the surveillance to the area in 2010, continued with the inertia of social norms to comply with the fisheries law, even two years after that decision.

Starting with a fragmented and divided fisheries sector, the main challenge was to construct a common vision of a sustainable future for the marine protected area and the economic development of the associated coastal communities. The marine protected area has inspired other neighbouring communities to propose another marine protected area of fishing interest on the Northern coast of Galicia (Decree 28/2009, of January 29, creating the Marine Reserve of Fishing Interest ‘Ría de Cedeira’), while a procedure for the extension of the marine protected area of *Os Miñarzos* has also been initiated and it is currently in the final stage. The objective is to move from the current protected area of 2,074 to 50,000 ha (in coastal waters), where eight fishing communities and 750 small-scale fishing vessels will potentially benefit. The case of *Os Miñarzos* also inspired other coastal communities not only in other regions of Spain (namely Catalonia and Andalucía), but also the new fisheries Law in Portugal as well as the Voluntary Guidelines for Securing Sustainable Small-scale Fisheries in the Context of Food Security and Poverty Eradication developed by the Food and Agriculture Organization. All of these initiatives inspired by the *Os Miñarzos* case have been highly positive to develop new sustainable trajectories and they are currently in different phases of development and degree of success. More recently, the transformative initiative initiated in *Os Miñarzos* served as the seed to create a new network of small-scale fishers in Latin America and the Caribbean, Portugal and Spain, involving more than 20 million of fishers.

2.1.13. A note on global visions centred on population growth

Although the World human population growth rate is reported to have declined from 2.1% per annum at the end of the 1960s, to below 1% in 2020, population still grew by 78 million people in 2022 (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2022). Population growth is recognized as a transformative force on planet Earth (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2022) and one which can be viewed negatively in terms of detrimental effects of increasing demands of humans on nature as populations increase (Rees, 2023). A number of initiatives have been proposed to curb human population growth, either forcibly, e.g., China’s one-child policy (Hesketh & Zhu, 1997) or by providing women with informed choices and options (*Nigeria - Family Planning 2030*, n.d.). However, the role of population growth has also been considered positive in terms of carbon neutralization in low-income, larger-sized families, in addition to boosting the working force through a younger global population (Yang et al., 2023). Needless to say, the latter argument falls short once the younger generation grows old and there is a subsequently smaller work force if humanity auto-corrects its course as a result of climate change and a collapsing global economy (Rees, 2023). One inspiring vision related to population growth is that of “Shrink toward abundance” (*Population Balance*, n.d.) which envisions “a future where our human footprint is in balance with life on Earth, enabling all species to thrive”. This vision incorporates informed individual decision-making, ecocentrism and social justice¹⁹.

¹⁹ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

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Annex 2.2. Most transformative visions per sub-topic

Based on **table SM.2.2**, a set of “most transformative visions” (N=44) was identified for more detailed analysis of content²⁰. Context to these visions is provided in the section below.

Table SM.2.2. Quality criteria used for selecting the subset of most transformative visions. Based on the source indicated in the third column.

Quality criteria	Key features	Sources
Relevant for biodiversity	Desirable future state for nature and people that can contribute to achieving the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity, namely a world of living in harmony with nature where “by 2050, biodiversity is valued, conserved, restored and wisely used, maintaining ecosystem services, sustaining a healthy planet and delivering benefits essential for all people.” (CBD, 2024). The vision aims at reversing biodiversity loss and nature's decline and encouraging its equitable and sustainable use. The vision addresses the major drivers of nature's decline and nature’s contributions to people and addresses how quality of life can be enhanced.	(CBD, 1992, 2010, 2022)
Multi-dimensional	The vision contributes to transformative change, considered 'a fundamental, system-wide reorganization across technological, economic and social factors, including paradigms, goals and values'. Transformative change is purposefully enacted in the quest for sustainability and equity. It addresses views, structures and practices and indirect drivers. It rearranges power relations.	(IPBES, 2019); Definition of transformative change from chapter 1; partially overlapping with the systemic criterion from Wiek & Iwaniec (2014).
Motivational	The vision inspires and motivates people and organizations towards the envisioned change. It motivates them to take actions and change behaviour to create a more sustainable society. It includes positive images about the future, speaking to emotions.	Wiek & Iwaniec (2014) and references therein.
Relevant	Composed of salient goals that focus on people, their roles and responsibilities. A vision is more likely to succeed if people recognize their roles and responsibilities in terms of who is doing what, where, why, how and its implications for nature and people. The visions should be relevant for key stakeholders and decision makers.	Wiek & Iwaniec (2014) and references therein.

²⁰ Content analysis of most potentially transformative visions (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10252510>)

Plausible	Evidence-based—informed by empirical examples, theoretical models and pilot projects. A vision is better if built on evidence or documentation about the relationship between nature and people and the causal mechanisms driving transformative change.	Wiek & Iwaniec (2014) and references therein.
Tangible	Composed of clearly articulated and detailed goals which help people to envision what the future may look like. The visions can include storylines that are not too abstract for people to understand. Visualizations and graphics that are intuitive could help people imagine the desired future without being too specific.	Wiek & Iwaniec (2014) and references therein.

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Annex 2.3. Specific pathways to endpoints of nature futures framework

Specific pathways suggested as actionable ways of reaching some of the illustrative endpoints proposed by the Nature Futures Framework were identified based upon a clear link to transformative change and evidence provided by supporting references (**table SM.2.3**). Most pathways that can operationalize transformative change were the ones related to the Nature for Society corner of the triangle, which is unsurprising as this is where most effort to date has been focused, in part because of documented impacts of the instrumental use of nature on nature, biodiversity and ecosystem services. The remaining endpoints all had a similar number of possible combinations. Most of the pathways towards the Nature for Society corner are associated with the promotion of circular economy models and changes to the financial system, increasing the engagement of stakeholders and right holders, as well as implementing other mechanisms for achieving transformative governance²¹. Changes to values, beliefs and worldviews may be possible through maintaining or restoring relationships, respect, reciprocity, responsibilities and solidarity between people and nature (Nature as Culture/One with Nature) and recognition of Indigenous rights over their territories, waters and resources (Nature for Society-Nature as Culture). The recognition of nature’s (or its specific entities’) rights as intrinsic and relational values may be facilitated via the legal rights to nature (Nature for Nature-Nature as Culture) and strengthening of nature compensation policies (Nature for Nature-Nature for Society). The majority of pathways address only instrumental values of nature (and thus fall within the Nature for Society skeleton – about 30% of the total) or include both instrumental and relational values of nature (and thus falling within the interim space between the Nature for Society and Nature as Culture/One with Nature corners of the triangle – about 25% of the total). Less than 5% of the existing pathways coded are addressing intrinsic values of nature and less than 2.5% of fall within Nature for Nature and Nature as Culture/One with Nature space, indicating that much more work needs to be done here. 19% of the interventions were associated with including both instrumental and intrinsic values of nature and 18.5% were exclusively related to Nature as Culture/One with Nature²².

Table SM.2.3. Illustrative pathways of interventions seen within the context of the Nature Future’s Framework to achieve plural desirable futures of living in harmony with nature.

Scenario endpoints from Duran et al 2023	Underlying focus	Intervention	Who is involved?	Link to transformative change	Supporting evidence
Nature as Culture	Values, beliefs and worldviews	Restore and maintain a balanced relationship between people and nature, increasing connectedness to nature,	Governments; Indigenous Peoples and local communities; Civil society	Indigenous Peoples and local communities advocate that balance and harmony between people, ancestors, spirits, lands, water, rocks, animals, plants and the cosmos are key and would lead to transformative change;	(Barragan-Jason et al., 2023; IPBES, 2023)

²¹ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

²² Content analysis of the most transformative visions or interventions underlying pathways

		community and self		better nature connection improves sustainability more than expected	
Nature for Society / Nature as Culture	Values, beliefs and worldviews	Recognize management by Indigenous Peoples and local communities, particularly through the legal recognition of land tenure	Government (national, subnational, local); Indigenous Peoples and local communities	Indigenous and local knowledge accumulated over time is significant in complex ecological systems. Much of this knowledge and associated values and worldviews are encoded in Indigenous and local languages and strongly connected to local environments and practices. Provide models for alternative ways of living in harmony with nature, cultural alternatives to colonial modernity ²³ , e.g., circular time or connecting to pasts that are about maintaining cultural connections to place where the transformations need to happen in modernity ²³ in order to allow for diverse worldviews to be recognized. For example, <i>Pachama</i> is a global community that provides inspiration and training to regenerate the planet's ecosystems, bring justice to their communities and restore our relationships with the Earth for the purpose of creating a sustainable future that works for all.	(Ermine, 2007; IPBES, 2023; Lundquist et al., 2017; M'sit No'kmaq et al., 2021; Papadopoulos, 2021)
Nature for Society	Transformative governance	Implement circular economy, including using the Global Value Chain transformation	Intergovernmental organizations; Government (national); Finance sector; Private sector	Global value chains ²³ can play a role in social and environmental upgrading depending on their manner of governance. A lead firm's relational governance of its Guatemalan coffee value chain was found to be effective in meeting challenges. A relational approach improved mutual problem-solving,	(Hochachka, 2023)

²³ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

				collaboration and trust in situations of unprecedented complexity. Relational Global value chains may outperform business-as-usual in situations of climate uncertainty, supporting more circular economies.	
Nature as Culture / Nature for Nature	Values, beliefs and worldviews	Recognize the legal rights to nature based on its intrinsic and relational values	Government (national); Non-Governmental Organizations; Civil society	A legal instrument that enables nature, wholly or partly, to have inherent rights and the same legal protection as people and corporations. It enables the defence of the environment in court – not only for the benefit of people, but for the sake of nature itself. In March 2017, the Whanganui River in Aotearoa New Zealand was the first river to officially receive the status of a legal person. This approach is most consistently advanced by empowering Indigenous leadership.	(Kramm, 2020; O'Donnell et al., 2020; O'Donnell & Talbot-Jones, 2018)
Nature for Society	Governance	Actively engage in community led activities and support sustainability-oriented citizen led initiatives	Civil society;	Citizen and civil society initiatives are important drivers of new innovations, experimentations and push for new pathways	(Bennett et al., 2016; Pereira et al., 2018, 2019; Schwanitz et al., 2023)
Nature for Society	Financial power imbalances and inequalities	Change the existing incentive structure(s) and the international monetary system. e.g., international tax reform	Intergovernmental organizations; Governments (national, subnational, local); Science and educational Organizations; Private sector; Finance sector	Reforming the global financial system would relieve the financial and environmental pressures on low-income countries (e.g., creation of an international tax convention, a unitary tax system capable of a just and fair capture of wealth to support investment in health and environmental objectives)	(Dempsey et al., 2022; United Nations, Interagency Task-force on Financing for Development United Nations, 2021)
Nature for Nature /	Governance	Increase the capacity of the	Government (national,	Raise revenues through Loss and Damage	(Roe et al., 2023)

Nature for Society		State to support transformative change while recognizing past unequal legacies	subnational , local); Private sector	compensations for climate change and nature; enhancing and implementing mechanisms for mitigation, restoration and compensation for environmental damage, including financing; strengthen biodiversity compensation policies for development and infrastructure loss (compensation would address root causes of overdevelopment)	
Nature for Society / Nature as Culture	Governance	Support diverse and inclusive decision-making and implementation actions to protect the environment and to address unfair distribution of benefits	Government (national); Non-Governmental Organizations; Civil society; Finance sector;	Concrete actions range from street protest, public campaigns, local consultations, strikes, boycotts to foster more sustainable consumer choices and litigation, to diverse disruptive actions such as occupations of public spaces and blockades and many more. The actors and alliances involved in bottom-up actions are diverse and represent plural values and worldviews. They include grassroots organizations and movements, Indigenous Peoples and local communities, women collectives, urban dwellers), scientists and international NGOs, among others	(Escobar, 2020; Hajer et al., 2015; Jasanoff, 2005; Martinez-Alier et al., 2016; Navas et al., 2022; Pascual et al., 2021; Scheidel et al., 2020; Scoones et al., 2015; Tran, 2021)
Nature for Society	Inclusive governance ²⁴	Promote mainstreaming of nature into other sectors through building trust among governmental and other implementing agents for a whole-of-government and whole-of-society approach to	Intergovernmental organizations; Government (national, subnational , local)	higher mainstreaming efforts due to higher commitment among stakeholders	(Apte, 2007; Whitehorn et al., 2019)

²⁴ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

		leverage mainstreaming			
Nature for Society	Accountable governance	Establish information disclosure practices and legal standards (e.g., due diligence or reporting standards) for private action	Governmen ts (national); Private sector	Improvement of science communication is necessary to make information understandable for policymakers, policymakers need to feel accountable for establishing and enforcing these standards	(Draper et al., 2023; Mackie, 2021; Villiers, 2019)

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